

INFLUENCE OF GENDER ON STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS PHYSICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of gender on students' achievement and attitude towards physics in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study adopted quasi-experimental pre-test post-test design. A total of 138 students drawn out of three secondary schools from each of the three senatorial districts of Ondo State constituted the sample. The students in the three schools were taught using the normal classroom instructional method. Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Physics Attitudinal Scale (PAS) were developed, validated and used to generate the data for the study. The data collected were analysed descriptively using mean and standard deviation, and inferentially using ANCOVA. The results of the study showed that there was no significant influence of gender on students' achievement on Physics. It implies that female students were found to be as good as their male counterparts in achievement in Physics. The findings from the study also showed that attitude of students towards Physics was not determined by gender. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that the curriculum should be designed to be unbiased. Male and female students should be treated equally in the classroom while there should be sensitization for equality among the students.

Keywords: Achievement, Attitude, Classroom, Curriculum, Equality, Gender.

Introduction

The knowledge of Physics is important in understanding contemporary science and technology, and the valuable role that physics plays in the scientific development of a nation is never in dispute. Guzel (2004) viewed physics as a fundamental science which explains natural phenomenon and those produced in the laboratories. Physics deals with behaviour of objects under the action of given force and nature which could be explained theoretically and experimentally (Guzel, 2004). Physics influences all other branches of learning that deal with the material world (Adeyemo, 2010). It is one of the science subjects taught at the senior secondary level of Nigeria educational system. It is very important because it provides basic theories in technology in conjunction with Mathematics. It is the foundation of progress and basis of many fields of theoretical and applied knowledge in science and technology.

Despite the importance and significant role played by Physics education towards the development of Nigeria, there are a number of observable problems plaguing the teaching and learning of the subject, especially at the secondary school level. These problems, as observed by Jegede and Adebayo (2013), WAEC Chief Examiners' report (2017) and Adeyemi (2008) include negative attitudes of students towards physics, gender difference, poor science background among others.

Gender, according to Yang (2010) refers to the social attributes and opportunities associated with both male and female and the relationship between women and men, as well as the relations between girls and boys. American Psychologist Association (2011) refers to gender as the attitudes, feelings and behaviours that a given culture associates with a person's biological sex. Gender is socially and culturally oriented and therefore, it is dynamic.

Gender difference has continued to be an issue of concern to educators and researchers. In Nigeria, reports from some studies requesting female and male adolescents to indicate their choices of subjects revealed that the adolescents selected different courses that followed gender stereotypes. Male prefer mathematics and sciences while the female opted for reading and life sciences (Akanbi, 2004; Yoloye, 2004). Gender, according to Erylimaz (2004) contributed to poor achievement of students in Physics. Babajide (2010) in his research reported disparity in the education of girls and women in science and technology in Nigeria. Also studies of Ogunneye and Lasisi (2008) coupled with the findings of Gonzuk and Chargok (2001) revealed that the number of female who study physics in secondary and tertiary institutions is small compared to the number of males. However, in contrast to this, Owolabi (2013) revealed that gender is not the major issue in Physics practical work as male and female students performed equally in their practices or experimental work. The issue of gender disparity in relation to their achievement in Physics is still a controversial one as Okwo and Otubar (2007) observed that gender has significant influence on science achievement while Babajide (2010) in his study found that gender has no significant influence on achievement in science especially in Physics. Hence there is need for more studies in order to clarify the issue of gender differences of students in relations to their achievement in Physics.

Attitudes defined by Akinbobola (2009), is an opinion or general feeling about something. Attitude can also be described as a state of readiness, a tendency on the part of individual to act in a certain way (Adesina and Akinbobola, 2005). Attitudes are related to coping with, and management of the emotions occurring during learning process, and they play an important role in directing human behavior (Adedayo, 2015). The attitude of students contributes immensely to their progress.

Physics is perceived as a difficult subject to students from secondary schools to university. It is considered as the most problematic area within the realm of science, and it traditionally attracts fewer students than Chemistry and Biology (Rivard and Straw, 2000). Students negative attitude barriers science being about dislike for Physics courses and Physics teachers (Olusola and Rotimi, 2012).

The research conducted by Kolawole (2007) as well as the studies of Afuwape and Oludipe (2008) revealed that there are significant differences in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor skills of students on respect to gender. Fatoba and Aladejana (2014) in their study discovered a slight difference in attitude of the students in favour of females-students in Oyo State, Nigeria.

In contrast, Bilesanmi-Awoderu (2006) found out that there are no significant differences in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor skills of students on respect to gender. The findings of Sri, Mohammad, Ashadi and Ari (2017), indicated that male and female students show similar attitude toward science process skill indicators.

The differences in attitude of male and female students towards physics have been a controversial issue globally. This study therefore aimed at investigating the effects of gender on students' attitude towards physics in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher's observations from teaching and marking of Physics examinations in schools have shown that grades of students in Physics have remained low in both internal and external examinations. The reports of the Chief Examiners in both National Examination Council (NECO) and West African Examination Council (WAEC) also attested to these observations. One of the factors which seems to be responsible for these poor levels of performance might be the differences in attitude of male and female students towards Physics. It is observed that many researches on the influence of gender on students' performance have resulted in mixed reports. Therefore, this study aimed at investigating the influence of gender on students' achievement and attitude towards Physics in secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for the study:

1. What is the influence of gender on the achievement mean scores of students taught Physics in the three groups?
2. Is there any difference in the attitude of male and female students taught Physics in the three groups?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the achievement mean scores of male and female students taught physics in the three groups.
2. There is no significant difference in the attitude mean scores of male and female students taught physics in the three groups.

Research Design

The research design for this study is quasi-experimental of pre-test post-test randomized design. Three groups of students were used for collection. Students in the three

groups were taught reflection and refraction of light waves using normal classroom instruction methods. The experiment lasted for six weeks. A post-test was administered to the three groups to determine the effect of teaching in their attitude and achievement in Physics.

Population

The population for the study comprised all SSS II students in all secondary schools in the three senatorial districts of Ondo State. There are 590 public secondary schools with about 7,261 students offering physics as at the time of this study.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study consisted of 138 senior secondary school two (SSS II) students offering physics. The students were selected from three co-education public secondary schools across the senatorial districts of Ondo State using multi-stage sampling procedure. One Local Government Area from each of the three senatorial districts was selected using simple random sampling technique. One public secondary school was also randomly selected from each of the selected Local Government Area. Purposive sampling was then used for the selection of one intact SSS II Physics class from each of the schools selected.

Research Instruments

Two instruments titled: “Physics Achievement Test (PAT)” and “Physics Attitudinal Scale (PAS)” were used for the study. PAT consisted of 51 items of multiple choice standard structured questions which were drawn from the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) past objective questions. The instrument measured the performance of male and female students on projectile, reflection of waves and refraction of waves. The PAS was developed to measure the attitude of male and female students towards the learning of Physics. Section A of the scale elicited information on the students' bio-data such as name of school, gender and class while section, B comprised 40 – items questionnaire which measured the students’ attitude towards teaching and learning of Physics. It was structured in 4-points likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA) – 4 points, Agree (A) – 3 points, Disagree (D) – 2points and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1 point. The respondents were enjoined to tick appropriate options while the results were collated and scored for data analysis.

Validity of the Instruments

The two research instruments were given to experts in Science Education, and Test and Measurement for face, content and construct validities. PAS was also given to experts in Guidance and Counselling for necessary corrections and suggestions. All corrections made by these experts were effected.

Reliability of the Instruments

The reliability of the two instruments was ensured through the test retest method. The responses were collected and analysed using Pearsons Product Moment Correlation Analysis. Reliability coefficient of 0.91 was obtained for PAT and 0.83 was obtained for PAS respectively.

Data Analysis

The data collected were analysed descriptively to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANOVA) was used to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance

Result and Discussion

Question 1: In answering the question, achievement mean scores of male and female students taught physics in the three groups were computed and compared as shown in table 1 below.

Table 1: Achievement mean scores of students taught physics in the three groups by gender

Group	Male					Female				
	N	Pre-test		Post-test		N	Pre-test		Post-test	
		M	SD	M	SD		M	SD	M	SD
1	20	13.60	2.80	19.00	4.81	26	14.15	2.88	18.62	3.84
2	22	13.50	2.52	17.83	3.95	21	12.71	3.51	18.55	2.31
3	22	13.40	2.67	17.00	4.06	27	15.08	3.39	16.91	3.25

Table 1 shows that male and female students in group 1 had pre-test achievement mean scores of 13.60, and 14.15 prior to teaching. After being exposed to Physics contents, they had post-test achievement scores of 19.00 and 18.62 respectively. This implies that male students in group 1 had higher achievement mean scores than their female counterparts in the same group. From the table, male and female students in group 2 had pre-test achievement mean scores of 13.50 and 12.71 before teaching. After their exposure to Physics contents, they had post-test achievement mean scores of 17.83 and 18.55 respectively. This implies that female students in group 2 had higher achievement mean scores than their male counterparts in the same group. Also, table 1 reveals that male and female students in group 3 had pre-test achievement mean scores of 13.40 and 15.08 before teaching. On exposure to Physics contents, they had post-test achievement mean scores of 17.00 and 16.91 respectively. This implies that both male and female students have approximately the same achievement mean scores.

Question 2: In answering the question, the attitudinal mean scores of male and female student in the three groups were computed and compared as shown in Table 2

Table 2: Attitudinal mean scores of students taught Physics by gender

Group	Male					Female				
	N	Pre-test		Post-test		N	Pre-test		Post-test	
		M	SD	M	SD		M	SD	M	SD
1	20	63.15	16.30	134.00	13.72	26	64.73	12.16	132.08	13.27
2	22	61.27	9.67	126.23	10.83	21	60.05	8.78	129.24	15.79
3	22	62.01	9.80	93.51	6.69	27	64.97	12.31	93.87	6.32

Table 2 shows that male students on the three groups had pre-test attitudinal mean scores of 63.15, 61.27 and 62.01 while female students had pre-test attitudinal mean scores of 64.73, 60.05 and 64.97 respectively. This implies that their pre-test mean scores are close. In group 1, male students had higher post-test attitudinal mean score (134.00) than their female counterparts (132.08) in the same group. In group 2, female students had higher post-test attitudinal mean scores (129.24) than their male counterparts (126.23) in the same group. However, in group 3, the post-test attitudinal mean scores of male and female students are very close (93.51 and 93.87). This implies that there is no significant difference in their post-test attitudinal mean scores.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: In order to test the hypothesis, the achievement mean scores of male and female students taught Physics in the three groups were analysed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) as shown in Table 3

Table 3: 2 x 3 ANCOVA of students' achievement in Physics by gender and group

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p
Corrected Model*	4388.165	6	731.361	70.656	.000
Covariate(Pretest)	42.259	1	42.259	4.083	.045
Sex*	2.572	1	2.572	.248	.619
Group	4328.248	2	2164.124	209.073	.000
Sex*Group	51.651	2	25.825	2.495	.086
Error	1344.987	131	10.351		
Total	94563.000	138			
Corrected Total	5744.152	137			

p<0.05

Table 3 reveals that there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test achievement mean scores of male and female students exposed to Physics concepts in the three groups. ($F_{2, 131}=2.495$, $p=0.086 >0.05$). The null hypothesis was not rejected. Similarly, the main effect of gender on students' achievement in Physics is not significant at 0.05 level of significance ($F_{1, 131}= 0.248$, $p=0.619 >0.05$). However, on exposure to Physics concepts, there is significant teaching effect on the students' achievement in the three groups. It is statistically significant at 0.05 level ($F_{2, 131}=209.073$, $p=0.000 <0.05$). Table 3 therefore implies that gender has no significant influence on students' achievement in Physics.

Hypothesis 2: In order to test the hypothesis, attitude mean scores of male and female students taught Physics in the three groups were computed and compared for statistical significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) as shown in Table 4

Table 4: 2 x 3 ANCOVA of students' attitude towards Physics by gender and group

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p
Corrected Model	101321.291	6	16886.882	115.927	.000
Covariate(Pretest)	.017	1	.017	.000	.991
Sex*	.575	1	.575	.004	.950
Group	99122.860	2	49561.430	340.234	.000
Sex*Group	144.741	2	72.371	.497	.610
Error	19082.593	131	145.669		

Total	1801222.000	138			
Corrected Total	120403.884	137			

p<0.05

Table 4 reveals that there is no significant difference in the attitude mean scores of male and female students taught Physics in the three groups. ($F_{2, 131} = 0.497, p=0.610 > 0.05$). The null hypothesis was not rejected. Similarly, the main effect of gender on students attitude towards Physics is not significant at 0.05 level ($F_{1, 131} = 0.004, p=0.950 > 0.05$). However, the teaching effect of Physics on students attitude is significant at 0.05 level ($F_{2, 131} = 240.234, p=0.000 < 0.05$). Table 4 thus implies that gender has no significant influence on students' achievement in Physics.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that students' achievement in Physics in the three groups in pre-test were low and did not differ statistically. This established the homogeneity of the three groups involved in the study.

The findings from this study showed that gender has no significant influence on the achievement mean scores of students in Physics. This implies that female students are found to be as good as their male counterparts in achievement in the three groups in the study. This is in variance with the finding of Eriba and Sesugh (2006) as well as Okwo and Otubar (2007) that gender has significant influence on science achievement. However, Babajide (2010) and Owolabi (2013) agreed that there was no significant influence of gender on students' achievement in science.

The study also found out that attitude of students towards Physics is not determined by gender, that is, the effect of gender on students' attitude towards learning of Physics was not statistically significant. This is in variance with the findings of Kolawole (2007) as well as Afuwape and Oludipe (2008). However, the findings from this study align with that of Babajide (2010) and Owolabi (2013) that gender is not the major issue in Physics as male and female students performed equally in their practices.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that gender has no influence on the achievement of students in Physics. From the study, it was also concluded that attitude of students towards Physics is not determined by gender.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- The curriculum should be developed in such a way that it will not be gender biased
- Male and female students should be treated equally in the classroom.
- Students should be sensitized and be made aware that their gender difference does not make a group more superior than the other.

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